

Designing for motivation and wellbeing: Reversal theory, doors, and colors

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Abstract Reversal theory recognizes the dynamic nature of the emotional experience of objects and spaces, and establishes a framework for design that can be used to enhance wellbeing. It also directly acknowledges the important effect that personal and social context has on motivations, affect and mental health. Reversal theory's focus on links between motivation and ensuing emotional states and behaviors, provides an important theoretical structure for the study of the individual's experience over time. The major tenets of reversal theory are discussed and their applicability by design practitioners reviewed. Ways that reversal theory can inform the design of architectural elements, for example, doors, and the development of interior design features, for example, via surface color selection, are discussed.

Keywords *Reversal theory, Wellbeing, Architecture, Interior design, Color*

Introduction

As many people in the developed and developing world become more concerned about using diminishing resources more effectively and efficiently, design that initiates and supports different motivational states, as appropriate or as needed, becomes more important.

One way in which different experiences can be organized and understood is in terms of the contrasting things that people want to experience at different times and in different situations, and such psychological desires will be what is meant here by 'motivational state.' The term comes from reversal theory (Apter, 1982, 2001, 2007), which is a general theory of motivation, emotion, and personality. This will provide the guiding structure for the present paper, which will apply it to architecture and interior design. Motivational states go beyond motivations as such in that they are associated with different ways of seeing the world and different styles of action. We should also notice that they are different from moods, the term 'mood' usually being used to refer to pessimism or optimism, thus being orthogonal to motivational states, which may be associated with any level of hope or despair.

The basic idea is that different architectural and interior design features will play a part in inducing different motivational states, and may also play a part in satisfying them emotionally. They are not the only stimuli to do so, but they are usually important. For example, a church induces a serious state of mind during a wedding and the need to do something significant, and also provides a setting that makes this emotional significance possible. Sometimes we choose the design situations in which we find ourselves for a reason tied to a motivational state. At other times these states just occur, outside our normal control.

Using the concept of motivational states to inform design decisions is consistent with the growing worldwide interest in positive design—the development of spaces, objects, and experiences that increase user subjective well-being and the likelihood of human flourishing. As Desmet and Pohlmeier say: "The intention [of positive design] is not to design so that people always feel good and never feel bad. Instead, it is to design such that people have a chance to embrace all the dimensions of life, including hardship, adversity, and opportunity" (Desmet & Pohlmeier, 2013, p. 16). The desirability of experiencing a full variety of different emotions, rather than just a few pleasant ones, is also a central idea in reversal theory.

Environmental psychologists have started on the road to linking design elements and emotional response to them. Their solutions to date have come up short because they view humans too simplistically and do not acknowledge the full richness of possible emotional experience and "the changeability of human nature" (Apter, 2007 p. xii). Reversal theory comprehensively reflects human beings' dynamic affective experiences, as described in the sections that follow.

The way that people change in their motivational states often arises from moving from one behavioral setting to another, for example from the office to the restaurant, the playground to the classroom. A complication is that a space can be used at different times and by different people as the context for varying activities. The same function room at a hotel can be used for the professional meeting or family birthday party. Design that directly acknowledges these variations in use and brings to bear features that will support these different states at different times increases the likelihood that object and space users will have affirming emotional experiences.

In our technologically advanced world, doors are an important architectural element in our experience. Which motivational state prevails will often depend among other things on various features of the settings - size of rooms, type of flooring, etc., all of whose psychological implications are cognitively integrated to holistically influence human experience and wellbeing. The door is the first contact with the new space and is therefore especially important in inducing a new state. Although many architectural features affect motivations, e.g. windows, pillars, carpets, here we are concentrating on doors, which will be used as illustrative of general concepts. We will also review links between surface colors seen and human experiences. In this way we shall be able to show how reversal theory can elucidate the effects of design both in terms of motivational states and of emotions. We are therefore not dealing here with a full range of architectural features (as in Koolhaas, 2014), or all forms of sensory stimulation, but have taken an example of each to illustrate the approach. But first we need to introduce reversal theory.

The reversal theory approach

Reversal theory is a useful system to inform the development of spaces where people will have their desired experiences (Fokkinga and Desmet, 2014a, b). Reversal theory posits that we move between different motivations for our actions in our daily lives, and in pursuing these contrasting needs we see the world in different ways. This means that, in a sense, each of us is a different person at different moments, and that over time we display diverse and even contradictory personalities: "We differ not only from each other, but also from ourselves. . . . [Reversal theory] offers a systematic description of the various ways that we can experience the world and act in it. The key idea is that there is a universal set of distinctive modes of interaction with the world, each one anchored in a different fundamental motivation. In the normal way of things and in our own unique fashion, we all move around between these different 'ways of being'" (Apter, 2007, pp. xi-xii). Reversal theory recognizes that every space/object use does not take place in the same psychological context.

Reversal theory recognizes four sets of experiences, each of which is identified by two opposite motivational states (Apter, 2001, 2007). At a particular point in time, one of each pair of states will be active, although some of the active states are having a more significant influence on overall psychological state than others. They have become the focus of attention. A person can move backwards and forwards between motivational states as an experience develops, and also from a focus on one pair of motivational states to another. This will all become clearer when we look at specific motivational states.

The eight motivational states

Reversal theory posits four pairs of opposite motivational states – states in which people want opposite things and see the world in reverse ways as a consequence (Apter, 1982). Note that these states are subjective and that reversal theory is therefore phenomenological in approach.

The first pair of states are the telic and paratelic motivational states. These can be conceptualized as involving diametrically opposed sources of pleasure in action. When someone is in a telic state, they derive satisfaction from the perception that they are advancing toward the completion of a goal and the actual, ultimate attainment of the acknowledged objective. Progress and improvement are important to someone in a telic state. If a person is in a paratelic state, pleasure is, instead, primarily derived from the activity in process, rather than from progress toward that goal - for example dancing or wine tasting. This means that sensory and kinesthetic experiences are important in the paratelic state, as is the feeling of being 'alive' in the moment. The telic state can be described by the adjective "serious," while the most appropriate adjective to describe the paratelic state is "playful." (Apter, 1982, 2007).

Emotionally, it is preferable to experience the telic state under low arousal conditions, which are experienced as relaxing; in highly energized states, the telic state gives rise to anxiety. The reverse is true for the optimal experience of the paratelic state; in a stimulating environment, the paratelic state is associated with excitement, while in a more relaxing environment boredom can ensue from the paratelic state. Research has shown that people prefer sensory experiences consistent with their motivational state, more relaxing experiences while they're in telic ones and more energizing conditions when they're in a paratelic state (e.g. Walters, Apter, and Svebak, 1982).

In all cases, the state is a precondition for an emotion. As Apter (2014) details, in the reversal theory system, after the telic state is induced, if there is high arousal, anxiety is experienced. It is not the case that after a person begins to feel anxious they enter the telic state, since it is the telic state which is a prerequisite for anxiety.

Reversal theory's second pair of states are the conforming and negativistic ones (Apter, 1981, 2001). This meta-motivational state moves beyond one's physical state to thoughts about one's own behavior. Actual behaviors are compared to relevant expectations or rules imposed by the salient culture. These rules may be any kind of subjective expectation, norm, social pressure, regulation, constraint, or requirement as seen by the person concerned. In a negativistic state people enjoy behaving in ways that violate such social conventions and experience their actions as a kind of freedom and independence. Conversely, in the conformist state a person likes acting in ways that seem to align with societal norms, and it would be unpleasant not to do so. As with all motivational states, the negativistic state defines what one wants, rather than what one actually experiences. This is why it is called a motivational state. The negativistic state is essentially rebellious and the conforming state compliant.

The next pair of states relate to "felt transaction outcome," which means the degree to which one perceives oneself to be gaining or losing in some ongoing transaction. The autic state is self-centered

while the other-centered state is called “alloic.” In the alloic state, one’s primary concern is that someone else should benefit from what is going on. If one is in the autic state the concern is for the self; gain will be felt as pride at having done well and loss as humiliation. In the alloic state any gain at the expense of others leads to the emotional state of shame while loss at the hands of others is experienced as pleasant modesty. It is important to realize that the other with whom we are interacting can be a person, a group of people, a situation, or an object. When dealing with an object, a person is most likely to be in the autic state, since it is difficult to identify with a screen and keyboard, for example. All the same, possessions can be treated in a caring selfless sort of way; in other words, they can be loved and attention devoted to them. This makes it possible to interact with an object in the alloic state (Apter, 2014).

Finally, there are two different ways of experiencing relationships. One is oriented to feelings of strength and power and called the “mastery” state. Being in it does not mean that you are powerful, but that this is what you want at a particular moment. The other state has to do with whether you have close emotional relationships; it is called the “sympathy” state. Being in the sympathy state implies that sympathy is what you want at that moment, not that you are necessarily experiencing it. In the mastery state, then, the goal is to feel powerful, and transactions are evaluated accordingly. In the sympathy state the overriding aim is to feel that others have fond feelings for you, or you for them, and transactions are, again, assessed in light of this desire. People in the mastery state may be described as “competitive,” while those in the sympathy state can be seen as “affectionate.”

“Reversals” are switches from one motivational state to its opposite within a pair, and these “flips” can occur fairly frequently. As mentioned earlier, they can result as one moves between different behavioral settings, say from bed to the breakfast room. More generally reversals occur when events happen that call on different states of mind, for example when someone tells a joke, or offers you a cigarette, or is rude. As Kerr, Hayashi, Matsumoto, and Miyamoto, report, reversal theory “is important for understanding human psychological responses to different types of locations, settings and activities” (Kerr, Hayashi, Matsumoto, & Miyamoto, 2002, p. 361). They state that their findings indicate that different motivational “states and arousal levels are affected by different settings” (p. 361).

Reversals can also occur spontaneously, with no obvious environmental cause, although one must suppose that internal processes of change are taking place. For example, one might be looking after a sick friend and at a certain moment, with nothing in the environment changing, suddenly want to pay more attention to one’s own needs. The alloic (other-oriented) state has, as it were, satiated and the autic (self-oriented) state has taken over. As a result one’s immediate emotions might switch from feelings of virtue to feelings of resentment at one’s friend.

So at any one time, there will be four active motivational states, one from each pair. For example a child doing a classroom test might experience telic, conforming, mastery and autic states at the same time, although one of them will be typically the dominating state, e.g., the telic state. However, the focus may change as the environmental demands change, for instance the teacher demands that the children copy something from the blackboard, which might induce a focal change to the conforming state in the children, all the other states remaining unchanged. Or perhaps the teacher makes a joke. This time the change from the telic to the paratelic state would be a reversal (from telic to paratelic) rather than a focal change. All this may seem complicated, but this complexity is missed by approaches that do not take into account the changeability of the way that motivation is experienced.

Doors

Doors serve multiple purposes in our physical and social environments. They not only allow the flow of light, air, information, and people into and out of a space, but send nonverbal, silent messages via their form and design. Doors are found inside structures and at the barriers between inside and outside. In this text, we shall focus on exterior ones because they have more generally been the focus of social science research (for example, Marsden, 1999).

Doors, whether domestic, commercial, or civic, are an example of an architectural design element that can take different forms and induce and support various motivational states. They are particularly of interest to reversal theory, because doors are often the site of reversals as one moves from one environment to another.

Their form and position have more complex implications than one might at first suppose. Doors are open or closed, which is another way of saying exposing or concealing, or allowing passage or not allowing passage. They may have an owner inside and a visitor outside, an owner both inside and outside at different times, a visitor both inside and outside at different times, and, less usually, an owner outside and visitor inside. The owner usually owns the door as well as the area behind the door.

The state invoked by the door should be the same as the state invoked by the building as a whole, otherwise the architecture will be psychologically incoherent and most probably negatively evaluated; the mental implications of all physical stimuli in a space are integrated cognitively so that they can, ideally, in a coordinated way, influence mental state (Kaplan & Kaplan, 1982). The door acts as a frame to the building and therefore should not contradict it. This frame-like quality is emphasized where there is an arch around the door.

Environmental factors are powerful nonverbal communicators, as evidenced by the work of Moezzi and Goins (2011). Doors can induce and subsequently support a message and state after they are viewed and, generally subsequently, experienced haptically or

in some other manner. If the people who own and visit a door, for example, those who are on opposite sides of it, share cultural context, they will “hear” the same nonverbal messages when they see, touch, etc., a door. For example, all will consistently perceive when a door indicates mastery; the visitor will see the owner as motivated by mastery and the owner will see himself/herself as motivated by mastery. A stout door with bars might help the owner to feel powerful (mastery), but it might produce feelings in the visitor that are more like mastery losing, or perhaps the visitor’s emotional state becomes that of conforming.

The focus in this text is on the state that doors invoke in visitors to a space, not in the owners of it. In some cases, for example when arriving at a health clinic, the visitor will already be in a given motivational state, with certain needs, and how the door can help satisfy these needs is a significant part of our discussion.

Also, just as the individual does not have enduring motivational states, we may suppose that a door has different effects on different people at different times, or even on the same person at different times. The person viewing the door could interpret information they’re drawing from it in different ways because of their personal context. For example, seeing the same healthcare door before and after a diagnosis of cancer is likely to be linked with a different motivational state. Or, perhaps in the face of a stout door, an individual in the autic state might feel that they are losing, but if they are in the alloic state, and empathize with the strength of the owner, they could feel good.

Doors and states

Let us suppose we have a closed door and a visitor coming to the door. What features of the door are likely to induce each motivational state in that visitor? This is the situation of most interest to the designer. We shall suggest here some features that might induce and even support each state; although personal and social factors also, for example, help establish state (Apter, 1982). This will provide structure for future research; state-inducing features discussed are derived from the environmental psychology literature. It should be noted that door examples provided are not the only doors that might induce or support a motivational state and that doors are not the only influence on state.

Telic state

The aim of the telic door is to get the visitor into a serious state of mind. The building might be a law court, or a hospital, or a bank. A door that induces a telic state might be larger than normal (consistent with the research of Lakoff & Johnson, 1999) or be made from expensive materials. The door on the entrance to the main headquarters of the Bank of England meets these criteria. Double rather than single doors, as on churches, are likely to be used to help induce the telic state.

Paratelic state

The aim of a paratelic state-inducing door is to get the visitor into the playful state of mind. It might be found

at a cinema, a casino, a sports stadium, or a swimming pool. These sorts of doors could feature bolder, more saturated colors (Valdez & Mehrabian, 1994) and curved shapes (Dazkir & Read, 2012). They could be unusually designed, for example wide doors or doors that don’t swing on a hinge but roll along overhead pipes to open and close (i.e., barn doors). Their hardware is likely to be more whimsical than telic state-inducing doors. These sorts of doors are likely to seem less practical, and are more likely to be installed purely for aesthetic enjoyment by the user group. Doors to many attractions at Disneyland fit this criterion.

Conforming state

The aim of conforming state-inducing doors is to get the visitor into a compliant state of mind. They are probable at a secure building at an airport, or a police station, or a church. These doors are likely to be symmetrical (Bajaj & Bond, 2016), large, and elevated (Lakoff & Johnson, 1999). They might also be revolving since these entrances are more effortful to use; entry needs to be carefully timed. A door without a knob, that is opened using something like a retinal scan, and only openable in the case of that appropriate retinal scan, would also be likely to induce a conforming state.

Negativistic state

The aim of a negativistic state-inducing door is to get the visitor into a rebellious state of mind. It might be used on a bar or club. This sort of door might be graffiti covered (intentionally by owners, not by vandals) and more rectilinear than curvilinear (Dazkir & Read, 2012). Its form is likely to bring to the owner’s individuality to mind because of the way it is personalized. An example: A metallic, spiky holiday wreath, without natural or curving elements on a door might induce the negativistic state. No information might be provided to visitors about hours of operation on a negativistic state-inducing door, for example. This door might be so narrow it is hard to pass into or out of a space. It should be painted in saturated not bright colors (Valdez & Mehrabian, 1994).

Autic state

The aim of the autic state-inducing door is to get the visitor to give priority to his/her own needs. This sort of door is appropriate at a spa, a hairdresser, or an emergency ward. It would feature a prominent welcome sign and, as relevant, directions for users, such as operating hours. These doors would be familiar in materials and scale, for example, painted wood for front doors for residences. Studies have repeatedly linked familiarity and comfort (Devlin, 2010). The form and style of these doors would vary over time based on current societal needs/practices. Another example is a bead curtain door, easily passable by all, as well as any door that can’t be locked or blocked – but of course these free-entry options aren’t really practical for the outer door of most buildings.

Alloic state

The aim of the alloic state-inducing door is to get the visitor to give priority to others. The building might be

a hospital waiting room or a charity shop. In this case, a “thank you” sign might greet visitors, or a sign saying “Please give patients priority through these doors.” Frosted glass may also help the visitor to be aware of the position of others on the other side of the door, thus not pushing the door into them.

Sympathy state

The aim of the sympathy state-inducing door is to get the visitor into an agreeable state of mind. It might be used on a hospital or a kindergarten. It should feature not very saturated but relatively bright colors (Valdez & Mehrabian, 1994) and be easy to open. Doors that open automatically are seen as very welcoming (Ju & Takayama, 2009). Just as rectilinear elements/decorations on challenging doors would establish a feeling of hostility, curvy ones here would be linked to more comforting and comfortable experiences (Dazkir & Read, 2012). Doors with visible wood grain would be sympathy inducing (Fell, 2010).

Mastery state

The aim with a mastery-state inducing door is to get the visitor into the competitive controlling state of mind. It might be used at a sporting venue, such as a swimming pool or golf course, or at a boardroom. Doors likely to induce mastery can be reminiscent of the doors to old time castles - massive and impenetrable, with the materials ranging from heavy/relatively coarse timbers to metal to something else that seems cold and hard. The doors could seem very mechanical and functional, perhaps gliding open as the visitor approached. They could also contain a peephole, as in Prohibition speakeasies, which might intimidate the visitor.

We should bear in mind that the relationship between doors (or any architectural feature) and motivational state, can become complicated. For one thing, there will normally be different cues in a given situation and the feature of interest, say a door, must compete with these others (windows, ceiling, etc.) in bringing about or inhibiting a reversal on one or another reversal dimension. Secondly, the same feature may support different states, for example a fireplace may support both the paratelic and mastery states, and this relationship may even change from one time to another in a given person. And of course the relationships may vary significantly from one person to another.

Colors and states

Surface colors have a significant effect on mental state (Valdez and Mehrabian, 1994). As a result, this interior design element is an important consideration for people applying reversal theory (Apter, 2014).

Valdez and Mehrabian (1994) empirically established a universal link between color saturation and brightness and pleasantness and energy level. Colors that are not very saturated but relatively bright have been linked to relaxation (and therefore support desirable telic state experiences) while seeing colors that are saturated but not very bright are pleasantly energizing to look at (and therefore support desirable paratelic state experiences). Colors that are less saturated seem

to have more gray in them than colors that are more saturated. For example, khaki green is less saturated than Kelly green. Responses to several hues also seem to be universal (Aslam, 2006; Elliot et al., 2007; Lichtenfeld et al., 2012). Hues are collections of wavelengths gathered into sets and named, such as green and orange.

Telic state

As used in many domestic and commercial applications, grays are the sort of not very saturated but bright color that Valdez and Mehrabian have empirically tied to calmer, relaxed emotional states (1994). Grays as light shades of black are associated with seriousness and sophistication in quantitative studies (Labrecque & Milne, 2013). Specific research has linked particular colors to certain functionalities that indicate serious thought. For example Lichtenfeld et al. have tied seeing the color green to improved performance on creative tasks via experiment-based research (2012). Integrating this research: use of colors such as a bright sage green is appropriate for a knowledge worker’s workspace; it will support the sort of mental state that leads to successful performance of complex cognitive tasks.

Paratelic state

Bold primary colors, such as a classic, pumpkin orange, are likely to support a paratelic state (Valdez & Mehrabian, 1994; Labrecque & Milne, 2013). The saturation and brightness levels of these colors have been linked to higher energy levels and orange, for example, is also associated with unsophisticated fun.

Conformist state

Rigorous research establishes that using a currently popular, bright but not very saturated color choice for a space, such as yellow in a kitchen in the United States, can support a conformist state (Valdez & Mehrabian, 1994; Anon., 2012). Using the common color for the space will make socially accepted rules of behavior in the area more compelling to space users (Labrecque & Milne, 2013).

Negativistic state

Empirical research focused on sporting events has linked seeing the color black with a negativistic-type state (Webster, Urland, & Correll, 2012).

Autic state

Seeing one’s own favorite color makes an autic-type state more probable according to careful research reported by Veitch (Veitch, 2012). Having preferred sensory experiences has been linked to positive moods; preferred colors are often tied to pleasant prior-life experiences and have the capacity to bring them top of mind.

Alloic state

Viewing a warm color makes being in an alloic state more likely (Mehta, Chae, Zhu, & Soman, 2012). Mehta and his team established via data collected in carefully designed experiments that looking at these shades was linked to a greater propensity to engage in philanthropic behavior.

Sympathy state

Seeing a blue surface is likely to induce a sympathy state, research suggests (Aslam, 2006; Labrecque & Milne, 2013). Worldwide, seeing the color blue has been linked by empirical investigations to trusting the thing or object presented in this color, either symbolically (e.g., in a logo) or concretely.

Mastery state

Viewing a red surface makes a mastery state more probable ("Stop on Red! The Effects of Color May Lie Deep in Evolution. . ." 2011). As reported in "Stop on Red," researchers Kralik, Khan, Levin and Dobson have linked seeing red to attempts to compete with others, for example.

One note of caution here: different researchers use motivational and emotional terms in different ways. It is therefore not sure, for example, that a word like 'energizing' is synonymous with 'arousing,' or 'trusting' the same as 'caring. So we should treat the relationships just outlined with some caution and use them as indications for further research. Ideally such research will make use of standard reversal theory psychometric scales, such as the Reversal Theory State Measure (Desselles, Murphy & Theys, 2014).

Conclusions

One final point here: Many buildings and rooms have multiple functions, and serve the needs of people in different motivational states. The need for this is emphasized by reversal theory. We need to develop straightforward ways to change the features of rooms to induce or sustain different states, e.g. furniture that can be easily rearranged, screens that can be repositioned/changed, alternative background colors that can be modified electronically, seats that can pivot from having one view to another, etc.

This paper has initiated the process of formalizing and systematizing the relationship between different design features and motivational states. We have illustrated this specifically by reference to doors and to surface colors. But of course, the theory relates in principle to every architectural feature and design variable. Reversal theory supplies a comprehensive structure to inform design decisions, one that can usefully be applied to a wide range of such decisions, from the selection of objects (e.g. ornaments) and furniture in rooms to the form of rooms and buildings themselves. Successful architects and designers no doubt already, intuitively, understand some of the kinds of relationships that have been discussed in this paper, but the aim here has been to start to lay the foundations of a more systematic and general study of the way that motivational states enter into the success or otherwise of particular objects and building.

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